

COESO

connecting research and society

COLLABORATIVE ENGAGEMENT ON SOCIETAL ISSUES

WP3 - Development of the Virtual Ecosystem for
Research Activation (VERA)

VERA Dashboard

date 23.12.2022

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COESO has received funding from the EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (2014-2020)
SwafS-27-2020 - Hands-on citizen science and frugal innovation, under Grant Agreement No.101006325

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Deliverable 3.3

VERA Dashboard

Grant Agreement number	: 101006325
Project acronym	: COESO
Project title	: Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues
Funding Scheme	: H2020-EU.5. - SCIENCE WITH AND FOR SOCIETY
Topic	: SwafS-27-2020 - Hands-on citizen science and frugal innovation
Project's coordinator Organization	: EHESS-OpenEdition
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WP and tasks contributing	: WP3, Task 3.3 Dashboard design and development
WP leader	: Net7
Task leader	: Net7
Dissemination level	: PU
Due date	: 31/12/2022
Delivery date	: 23/12/2022
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Contents

I. Executive summary	4
I. Structure of the document	5
II. The ratio behind VERA structure	5
III. VERA UI kit	6
IV. VERA mockups	7
V. Dashboard user testing	8
VI. Plan for future implementations	9
VII. Conclusions	10

I. Executive summary

The aim of this document is to complement the release of the actual Deliverable 3.3 - VERA Dashboard, due in M24 (31st December 2022).

The deliverable is the outcome of Task 3.3 *Dashboard design and development*, whose goal is to design the frontend web application, which allows users to build projects and to collaborate by discovering new project partners, and funding opportunities and to start a conversation exploiting the messaging tool.

This task took advantage of the activities carried out under Task 3.1 User research and user experience design and documented in an accompanying document published as Deliverable 3.1 that was released in April 2022¹.

The VERA - Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation dashboard will be accessible from <https://vera.operas-eu.org/> and its launch will be announced in early January 2023.

To design the final look and feel of VERA, we decided to start from the design of the GoTriple² platform, because both VERA and GoTriple will be incorporated as a service under the OPERAS research infrastructure. For this reason we would like the two platforms to be coherent and communicate to the users that they belong to the same ecosystem.

Compared to the GoTriple UI kit, we decided to keep the original structure of the components that will also be useful in VERA, to use a similar font stack, and the same structural colors (grayscale color palette used for background and borders) while the brand colors of GoTriple (red, yellow, and purple) will be replaced by the branding colors of VERA.

The components from the GoTriple UI kit that will be reused in VERA are:

- Buttons
- Tags
- Header
- Footer
- User profiles previews
- Modals
- Form elements
- Navigation elements: tab bar and vertical navigation
- Wizard element

The design of the VERA dashboard keeps on following the iterative approach of the overall design. A first user testing activity is taking place by the time of the release of this deliverable. The results of this first user testing are being incorporated into the public version of the platform that will be announced in early January 2023.

A second round of user testing is planned to take place by April 2023 to incorporate comments from users external to COESO.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/6523503#.Y6Vix-zML9E>

² <https://gotriple.eu/>

I. Structure of the document

This document is structured in VII main sections, describing:

- The VERA general structure (chapter II)
- The main features of the UI Kit (chapter III)
- The screenshots of the VERA mockups (chapter IV)
- Chapter V describes the user testing activity
- In chapter VI it is briefly described the plan for future evolutions until M36
- Conclusions are described in Chapter VII

II. The ratio behind VERA structure

The general structure of VERA has constantly evolved and the deep and complex design process is reflected in the development of the platform's interface design. The different phases of the design can be broken down as follows:

- Benchmarking
- User research
- Sketches and wireframing
- High fidelity prototypes³
- UI kit definition and creation
- Visual design
- Co-design workshops
- Team validation
- Usability testing and qualitative analysis

The interface unites brand guidelines and user requirements to achieve its main goal: creating a nicer, more fluid and more attractive experience for anyone who wants to contribute to SSH (social science and humanities)-focused citizen science. It connects them and allows them to begin collaborating with each other in a better way, as well as giving users tools to share and promote their projects.

Some of the main functionalities of the platform currently under finalization are:

- Creating a project to give visibility to the work and its results
- Browsing projects to collaborate, follow or share
- Discovering other users with different interests, backgrounds and expertise
- Creating a team by inviting team members
- Sharing thoughts, notes and results using a project diary, publicly or just between team members
- Exchanging messages on Mattermost
- Searching for funding for a future project
- Creating a toolbox to access multiple tools from one place

³ A demo of the prototype is accessible through this video, released in August 2022: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ptuqj3P-GeM>

III. VERA UI kit

In order to lay the foundations of the proper development and growth of VERA interface that can easily adapt and scale far into the future, we created a UI Kit which both creates a design bridge with the GoTriple platform, as mentioned above, and describes new components developed for the specific needs of the interface and its main goals. Furthermore, the UI Kit creates standards that guide these components as to how they should work together to create consistency.

The UI summarizes a whole ecosystem of guidelines related to different functionalities, entities, states and, of course, the style of the interface elements.

Some of the main assets of the UI kit developed till now are:

- Color system
- Typography system
- Grid system and layout
- Icons
- Backgrounds
- Buttons: primary, secondary, tertiary
- Form elements: input and select
- Tags: topics, interests, skills
- Header
- Footer
- Accordion
- Preview: user profiles, projects, funding
- System: toast, tooltips
- Navigation elements: tab bar and vertical navigation
- Modal

IV. VERA mockups

Below are inserted the main mockups of the VERA dashboard.

- The projects page allows users to browse and search among the public projects.
- The project page allows external users to see the public details: summary, main goals, useful links, team members, project diary updates. It is also possible to contact the members of the project via Mattermost.
- Public profiles can be browsed through the VERA profile page. For every public user it is possible to see the projects in which they are involved, the bio, languages spoken, interests, skills. It is also possible to contact these people via Mattermost to establish collaborations

A simple procedure guides users in the steps of setting up new project(s). Through the dashboard it is possible to set up the project description, decide the collaboration tools, and invite members to join the team.

V. Dashboard user testing

A first round of moderated user testing was conducted between November and December 2022 to test the main features developed thus far and to improve the user experience in anticipation of a public launch. At the time of writing, four user test sessions have been conducted: three with pilot participants and one with a GoTriple collaborator. A fifth test with another external collaborator is scheduled to take place on December 23rd.

For this initial round of tests, participants were asked to complete 8 tasks given by the moderator. These tasks centered around:

1. Filling in VERA account information
2. Viewing one's profile page
3. Creating a project
4. Completing project setup
5. Writing a project diary post
6. Promoting the project
7. Viewing and managing team members
8. Adding and removing tools

After each task, a series of questions were asked to rate the ease-of-use, time taken to complete the task and support information received during the completion of the task. For tasks 5-8, an additional question was asked to rate the usefulness of the features tested. These questions followed the user testing guidelines provided by the ASQ usability⁴ testing framework. At the end of the session, participants were asked to evaluate the overall ease-of-use and overall

⁴ Lewis, J. R. (1995). IBM computer usability satisfaction questionnaires: Psychometric evaluation and instructions for use. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 7, 1, 57-78.

usefulness of the platform. For each question, participants were asked to rate on a scale from 1 (I don't agree at all) to 5 (I completely agree).

Initial results from these tests indicate that the overall usability is indeed satisfactory, with a median score of 4 out of 5. Some aspects of the user experience that are still in need of improvement and are currently being addressed include guiding users through their VERA account completion and addressing some bugs present in the account fields, onboarding the user between project creation and project setup, and the presentation of the Tools section and its features.

In terms of usefulness, some confusion over the intended purpose of the platform stands out. For three participants, VERA is an excellent promotional tool as well as a more useful and engaging replacement for a static project website or blog. One participant expressed excitement about the ability to create a toolbox with custom links to monthly meetings and frequently used files. Yet another participant hopes to be able to share their selected tools on the public project page and add custom, specialized SSH-related tools. However, some participants questioned the focus on tools and wondered how much active collaboration would take place on the platform itself. It should be noted that the version of VERA tested is lacking many features that are currently in the final stages of development such as the Mattermost integration, custom tool links for shared folders or monthly meetings, as well as funding search capabilities (all to be implemented in early 2023). Therefore the usefulness of the platform might not have been seen as totally satisfactory. We expect the overall perceived usefulness of the platform to increase substantially with the addition of the aforementioned features and the quality-of-life improvements in development. Regardless, resolving the usability and usefulness issues is the target for the design indication resulting from these user tests and will be implemented in an iterative manner, prioritizing the most critical issues first.

To test a more-or-less complete version of VERA, and taking into account the issues highlighted by the first five tests, an expanded second round of user testing is planned to take place before April 2023 with participants external to the COESO project.

VI. Plan for future implementations

In keeping with an Agile approach, the plan for future implementations is to improve the platform usability according to the user testing results.

In parallel, platform enhancements are planned by inserting new functionalities and integration:

- integrate the Fundit tool to identify and suggest possible funding opportunities for projects
- integration with EU-Citizen.Science platform to increase projects visibility
- the release of the matchmaking tool that will allow users to identify potential projects where they could contribute on one hand, and identify potential collaborators on the other hand.

Leading up to M36 (December 2023), when the final VERA release is expected, additional improvements and ideas for further integrations may arise thanks to the users comments and continuous listening for community feedback.

VII. Conclusions

The design of the VERA dashboard is the final result of the previous activities carried out in WP3. The overall process that started in early 2021 with a benchmark activity, passing through the co-design workshops up to the active involvement of COESO project partners resulted in a robust and convincing design for VERA, which stands for Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation.

The aim of the platform is to become a hub where researchers and key society stakeholders (community-based organizations, experts of practice, service providers, politicians, journalists, etc.) can meet and collaborate to identify and solve societal issues through SSH (social science and humanities)-focused citizen science.

The co-design concept is at the heart of this approach and was also at the heart of the VERA platform design.

The overall look and feel of VERA has been designed in order to be aligned with the OPERAS ecosystem, VERA being one of its services, and at the same time to be clearly recognizable and unique as a web product. This approach is key also in the light of the sustainability of the platform itself.

The agile methodology adopted in the design and development of VERA is being kept alive and will continue not only until the end of the project but also beyond with the mission of providing a live platform in line with the evolving needs of its community of users.